

Utilization of Hydrogen As an Energy Storage Vector By a Combined Reversible High Temperature Electrolysis and Compressor System Integrated with Upstream Biogas and Downstream E-Fuel Production

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Combining of high temperature rSOC electrolysis and Fischer-Tropsch synthesis to obtain drop-in paraffinic fuels with high efficiency.

Challenges

- Current predictions towards a hydrogen society and the extensive use of H₂ as a large-scale energy storage vector are emerging from the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources, especially wind and solar.
- At the same time, there is a huge global demand for sustainable and carbon-neutral fuels (e-fuels) in sectors that are difficult to electrify, e.g. aviation and maritime transport.
- Options such as the utilization (and capture) of CO₂ and biogas would be desirable features to be connected to the future energy systems. When the price of electricity is high, biogas is, along with hydrogen, a very suitable fuel for high-temperature solid oxide electrolyzer (SOEC).
- The key issues to make these new technical solutions based on clean energy techno-economically viable are:
 - 1) quick response time to changes in the price of electricity
 - 2) high system efficiency compared to established technologies
 - 3) versatility and fuel flexibility

Simplified PI-diagram of VTT's 10 kW rSOC system.

Research activities

- VTT has developed 10 kW reversible solid oxide (rSOC) system offering possibility to investigate the most relevant electrolyzer system research questions in very (cost) effective way, e.g. to investigate enthalpy and heat fluxes through the system and BoP components in detail.
- Investigation and development of the interface between H₂/syngas production and compression system (automation, control and safety systems etc.).
- Developing operation methods for rSOC in co-electrolysis mode, where the key parameters (T, i, inlet flow ratio of H₂-H₂O-CO₂) can be adjusted to achieve desired outlet gas composition for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis H₂/CO ≈ 2 (1.8-2.1) and MeOH synthesis (H₂-CO₂)/(CO+CO₂) ≈ 2.1.
- Syngas pressurization options are studied for downstream processes: ~30 bar for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis and ~50-60 bar for MeOH synthesis.
- Since the same electrolyzer-compressor system is used alternately for both syngas and high purity H₂ production, the high-precision H₂ quality control measurement procedure has been developed to meet the strict H₂ purity requirements of ISO-14687 standard. Especially the analysis of following impurities is of paramount importance: O₂ (< 5 ppm), H₂O (< 5 ppm), CO (< 0.2 ppm), CO₂ (< 5 ppm) and N₂ (< 300 ppm).

Process path to methanol synthesis, where the cleaned syngas from gasified biomass is upgraded with solid oxide electrolyzer (SOEC).

Our solution

- Reversible Solid Oxide (rSOC) technology is a good technology base for green, flexible and efficient energy systems offering the highest electrical efficiency (80-90%) in electrolysis mode and has also capability for co-electrolysis of steam and CO₂
- To enhance the utilization of H₂ as an energy storage vector, VTT has developed a combined 10 kW rSOC and compressor system for both H₂ storage and e-fuel production. Depending on the price of electricity, the developed rSOC system can be operated in 3 different modes:
 - 1) **Fuel cell (SOFC) mode** - where locally stored hydrogen or biomethane is used to produce electricity for the local electricity grid
 - 2) **Electrolyzer (SOEC) mode**, where ultra-pure hydrogen (suitable for vehicle applications according to ISO-14687 standard) is produced and compressed for storage at 350 bar
 - 3) **Co-electrolysis (co-SOEC) mode**, where synthesis gas is produced and compressed for use in the production of e-fuels (or e-methanol) in downstream processes
- This demonstrated multifunctional energy concept can be further on used in the design of larger-scale integrated modular multi-fuel & multi-purpose energy storage concepts and local emission-free electricity production.

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